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Requirement Analysis of Black Box Testing

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Abstract

Black Box Testing is used when code of the module is not available. Black box testing treats the system as a “black-box”, so it doesn’t explicitly use knowledge of the internal structure or code. Or in other words the Test engineer need not know the internal working of the “Black box” or application. In such situations appropriate priorities can be given to different test cases, so that the quality of software is not compromised, if testing is to be stopped prematurely. This paper briefly sketches a general strategy for black-box testing, different methods involved and the advantages and disadvantages associated with them. The study of this paper would be beneficial to both researchers and practitioners alike in having an understanding of black box testing.

Keywords: *Black-Box Testing, White-Box Testing, Equivalence Class Portioning, Boundary Value Analysis, Decision Table.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Software testing methods are traditionally divided into white and black-box testing. These two approaches are used to describe the point of view that a test engineer takes when designing test cases.

1.1 White-box testing

White-box testing is used when the tester has access to the internal data structures and algorithms including the code that implements these.

1.2 Black-box testing

Black-box testing treats the software as a "black box"—without any knowledge of internal implementation. Black-box testing methods include: **equivalence partitioning, boundary value analysis, all-pairs testing, fuzz testing, model-based testing, exploratory testing and specification-based testing.**

Specification-based testing:

Specification-based testing aims to test the functionality of software according to the applicable requirements. Thus, the tester inputs data into, and only sees the output from, the test object. This level of testing usually requires thorough test cases to be provided to the tester, who then can simply verify that for a given input, the output value (or behavior), either "is" or "is not" the same as the expected value specified in the test case. Specification-based testing is necessary, but it is insufficient to guard against certain risks.

Advantages and disadvantages:

The black-box tester has no "bonds" with the code, and a tester's perception is very simple: a code must have bugs. Using the principle, "Ask and you shall receive," black-box testers find bugs where programmers do not. On the other hand, black-box testing has been said to be "like a walk in a dark labyrinth without a flashlight," because the tester doesn't know how the software being tested was actually constructed. As a result, there are situations when a tester writes many test cases to check something that could have been tested by only one test case, and/or some parts of the back-end are not tested at all.

Therefore, black-box testing has the advantage of "an unaffiliated opinion", on one hand, and the disadvantage of "blind exploring", on the other.

As we have seen, good test case design is the key to suitable testing of the SUT. The goal while testing a SUT is to detect most (hopefully all) of the defects, through as small a set of test cases as possible. Due to this basic goal, it is important to select test cases carefully—best are those test cases that have a high probability of detecting a defect, if it exists, and also whose execution will give a confidence that no failures during testing implies that there are few (hopefully none) defects in the software. There are two basic approaches to designing the test cases to be used in testing: black-box and white-box. In black-box testing the structure of the program is not considered. Test cases are decided solely on the basis of the requirements or specifications of the program or module, and the internals of the module or the program are not considered for selection of test cases. In this section, we will present some techniques for generating test cases for black-box testing. In black-box testing, the tester only knows the inputs that can be given to the system and what output the system should give. In other words, the basis for deciding test cases is the requirements or specifications of the system or module. This form of testing is also called functional or behavioral testing. The most obvious functional testing procedure is exhaustive testing, which is impractical. One criterion for generating test cases is to generate them randomly. This strategy has little chance of resulting in a set of test cases that is close to optimal (i.e., that detects the maximum errors with minimum test-cases). Hence, we need some other criterion or rule for selecting test cases. There are no formal rules for designing test cases for functional testing. However, there are a number of techniques or heuristics that can be used to select test cases that have been found to be very successful in detecting errors. Here we mention some of these techniques.

1.2.1 Equivalence Class Partitioning

Because we cannot do exhaustive testing, the next natural approach is to divide the input domain into a set of equivalence classes, so that if the program works correctly for a value, then it will work

correctly for all the other values in that class. If we can indeed identify such classes, then testing the program with one value from each equivalence class is equivalent to doing an exhaustive test of the program. However, without looking at the internal structure of the program, it is impossible to determine such ideal equivalence classes (even with the internal structure, it usually cannot be done). The equivalence class partitioning method tries to approximate this ideal. An equivalence class is formed of the inputs for which the behavior of the system is specified or expected to be similar. Each group of inputs for which the behavior is expected to be different from others is considered a separate equivalence class. The rationale of forming equivalence classes like this is the assumption that if the specifications require the same behavior for each element in a class of values, then the program is likely to be constructed so that it either succeeds or fails for each of the values in that class. For example, the specifications of a module that determines the absolute value for integers specify one behavior for positive integers and another for negative integers. In this case, we will form two equivalence classes—one consisting of positive integers and the other consisting of negative integers. For robust software, we must also consider invalid inputs. That is, we should define equivalence classes for invalid inputs also. Equivalence classes are usually formed by considering each condition specified on an input as specifying a valid equivalence class and one or more invalid equivalence classes. For example, if an input condition specifies a range of values (say, $0 < \text{count} < \text{Max}$), then form a valid equivalence class with that range and two invalid equivalence classes, one with values less than the lower bound of the range (i.e., $\text{count} < 0$) and the other with values higher than the higher bound ($\text{count} > \text{Max}$). If the input specifies a set of values and the requirements specify different behavior for different elements in the set, then a valid equivalence class is formed for each of the elements in the set and an invalid class for an entity not belonging to the set. One common approach for determining equivalence classes is as follows. If there is reason to believe that the entire range of an input will not be treated in the same manner, then the range should be split into two or more equivalence classes, each consisting of values for which the behavior is expected to be similar. For example, for a character input, if we have reasons to believe that the program will perform different actions if the character is a letter, a number, or a special character, then we should split the input into three valid equivalence.

Another approach for forming equivalence classes is to consider any special value for which the behavior could be different as an equivalence class. For example, the value 0 could be a special value for an integer input. Also, for each valid equivalence class, one or more invalid equivalence classes could be identified. It is often useful to consider equivalence classes in the output. For an output equivalence class, the goal is to have inputs such that the output for that test case lies in the output equivalence class. As an example, consider a program for determining rate of return for some investment. There are three clear output equivalence classes—positive rate of return, negative rate of return, and zero rate of return. During testing, it is important to test for each of these, that is, give inputs such that each of these three outputs is generated. Determining test cases for output classes may be more difficult, but output classes have been found to reveal errors that are not revealed by just considering the input classes.

Once equivalence classes are selected for each of the inputs, then the issue is to select test cases suitably. There are different ways to select the test cases. One strategy is to select each test case covering as many valid equivalence classes as it can, and one separate test case for each invalid equivalence class. A somewhat better strategy which requires more test cases is to have a test case cover at most one valid equivalence class for each input, and have one separate test case for each invalid equivalence class. In the latter case, the number of test cases for valid equivalence classes is equal to the largest number of equivalence classes for any input, plus the total number of invalid equivalence classes. As an example, consider a program that takes two inputs—a string s of length up to N and an integer n . The program is to determine the top n highest occurring characters in s . The tester believes that the program memory deal with different types of characters separately. There are mainly four types of equivalence classes exist.

- weak normal equivalence partitioning
- Strong normal equivalence class partitioning
- Weak robust equivalence class partitioning
- Strong robust equivalence class partitioning

1.2.2 Boundary value analysis

It has been observed that programs that work correctly for a set of values in an equivalence class fail on some special values. These values often lie on the boundary of the equivalence class. Test cases that have values on the boundaries of equivalence classes are therefore likely to be “high-yield” test cases, and selecting such test cases is the aim of boundary value analysis. In boundary value analysis, we choose an input for a test case from an equivalence class, such that the input lies at the edge of the equivalence classes. Boundary values for each equivalence class, including the equivalence classes of the output, should be covered.

In case of ranges, for boundary value analysis it is useful to select the boundary Boundary value test cases are also called “extreme cases.” Hence, we can say that a boundary value test case is a set of input data that lies on the edge or boundary of a class of input data or that generates output that lies at the boundary of a class of output data .

2. Black box strategies:

Black Box testing strategy focuses on the functional requirements of the software without any regard to the internal structure. It is used in most system level testing where functional, performance, recovery and security & stress are main issues. This applied strategy finds errors in incorrect or missing functions (compared to white box), interface errors, errors in external data structures and in behavior performance problems (Combinations of input make it behave poorly). It also finds errors in initialization and termination (Sensitive to certain inputs (e.g. performance). It is performed much later in process than white box.

A test strategy that uses every possible input condition as a test case would be ideal but is not possible. We apply following Black-Box Testing Strategies.

Graph Based Testing

The first step in black box testing is to understand the objects that are modeled in software and the relationships that connect the objects. Once this has been accomplished, the next step is to define a series of tests that verify all objects that have the expected relationship with another.

Equivalence Partitioning

It is a black-box testing method that divides the input domain of a program into classes of data from which test cases can be derived. It reduces, by more than one, the number of test cases that must be developed since one test case might uncover a class of errors. It covers a large set of other possible test cases hence helps reduce the number of inputs. Incorrect processing of all integer number is detected.

Identifying Equivalence Classes: Each input condition (a sentence or phrase in the specification) is taken & divided into 2 or more classes as valid equivalence class and nvalid equivalence class.

Rules for Equivalence Classes:

Range - If an input condition specifies a range (i.e. n is an integer from 1 to 10) then

1 valid (if $1 \leq n$ and ≤ 1000)

2 invalid (if $n < 1$ and > 1000)

1.2.3 Decision table

Decision tables are a precise yet compact way to model complicated logic.

Decision tables, like flowcharts and if-then-else and switch-case statements, associate conditions with actions to perform, but in many cases do so in a more elegant way.

Conclusion

In this paper the Black box testing techniques are used to generate test cases for black box testing, mainly three types of techniques are used.

1. Equivalence class partitioning

2. Boundary value analysis

3. Decision table

All the algorithms are wisely used to reach the desired goal of finding test cases or we can say that generating test cases, therefore these test cases can be implemented anywhere in the triangle testing or quadratic equation testing of any software which implements them. These test cases can be further counter-matched with the theoretical values or cases to provide a tester a much classified result and testing can be made easy.

REFERENCES

1. Manish Goyal, Computer Based Numerical & Statistical Techniques.
2. Udit Agrwal, Computer Based Numerical & Statistical Techniques.
3. http://en.wikibooks.org/wiki/Numerical_Methods/Equation_Solving
4. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Transcendental_function
5. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Newton's_method
6. http://mat.iitm.ac.in/home/sryedida/public_html/caimna/transcendental/bracketing%20methods/bisection/bisection.html
7. www.math.odu.edu/~jhj/chs2.pdf
8. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/False_position_method
9. http://web.mit.edu/varun_ag/www/ste_gas.pdf
10. http://www.jamesbrennan.org/algebra/intro%20to%20algebra/solutions_of_algebraic_equations.htm
11. <http://www.math.rutgers.edu/~erowland/polynomialequations.html>
12. <http://comsci.liu.edu/~vasilaky/dotnet/Csharpbook.htm>
13. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_flow_diagram
14. http://www.umsl.edu/~bcjtz4/umsl/er_diagrams.html
15. <http://www.edrawsoft.com/Flowchart-Definition.php>
16. <http://www.mathworks.in/matlabcentral/answers/112581-solving-transcendental-equation-numerically>
17. De Jong, "An Analysis of the Behavior of a Class of Genetic Adaptive Systems", 1975.
18. David E. Goldberg, "Genetic Algorithms in Search, Optimization and Machine Learning" (text), 1989